

Exergy Analysis of Gas Turbine Open Cycle with Pressure Gain Combustion Based on Humphrey Cycle

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Abstract. This paper describes an exergy comparison of the pressure gain combustion (PGC) gas turbine (GT) with conventional GT. PGC has recently emerged as a promising approach to achieve major performance improvements in the current gas turbines operating on the Joule cycle, where the potential for major performance upgrades has nearly plateaued. However, the inherently unsteady and periodic nature of this combustion technology presents challenges in modelling the PGC process and understanding its impact on the cycle. In this work, PGC is represented by a steady-state model of constant volume combustion based on the Humphrey cycle, along with a constant pressure combustion loss model for capturing practical losses. Exergy performance was analysed in terms of exergy destruction for three air-cooled GT cycles with different combustors: a conventional isobaric combustor, an optimistic PGC combustor with no losses and a realistic PGC combustor with losses. Gas turbine cycles were modelled in WTEMP (Web-based Thermo-Economic Modular Program) software, a modular and flexible cycle analysis tool developed by TPG at the University of Genova. Simulations were performed at compressor pressure ratios from 5 to 40 at turbine inlet temperatures of TIT=1300°C and TIT=1700°C, and results were analysed in terms of exergy destruction and exergy efficiency. It was found that a PGC combustor with optimistic losses recovers more exergy than a conventional combustor due to pressure gain. At a cycle pressure ratio of 20 and 1700°C TIT, the PGC combustor with a pressure ratio of 1.35 resulted in an exergy efficiency of 79.6% compared to 77.9% of the Joule combustor. However, with realistic loss from inlet pressure drop and constant pressure combustion in the PGC combustor, the PGC combustor showed higher irreversibility than conventional combustor but the overall benefit on the cycle was retained at low compressor pressure ratios. Moreover, the percentage increase in turbine irreversibility from blade cooling was found to be slightly lower for the PGC cycle as compared to Joule.

1. Introduction

Pressure gain combustion (PGC) has gained significant attention in recent years due to its theoretical potential for major efficiency improvements in modern gas turbines [1–3]. A PGC gas turbine is characterised by a rise in pressure during the cycle heat addition or combustion process. This pressure rise can be achieved by self-pressurisation of combustion products in constant volume combustion, such as in the Humphrey cycle [4] or through detonation combustion in Rotating Detonation Combustion (RDC)[5]. However, all PGC combustion devices are unsteady, generating a spatio-temporal non-uniformity in combustion outflow that presents challenges in developing reduced-order steady-state models of the PGC process for the system-level performance investigation [4,6,7].

Several studies have reported the thermodynamic performance benefit of PGC gas turbines through the first-law principle through component characteristics and energy balances [4,8–10].

For instance, Kentfield studied three different types of PGC engines and showed an increase in power output ranging from 6.5% to 9.6%, depending on the engine type [1]. Similarly, Jones et. al reported fuel reduction of 4-9 % through PGC combustion [2]. Heiser et al. [8] performed a cycle analysis at wide conditions by using a simplified PGC models based on pulsed detonation engine (PDE) and showed that the PGC cycle performs better than Joule at low-pressure ratios due to higher combustor exit enthalpy and reduced cycle entropy generation. PDEs were found to perform better than real Brayton cycles only for compression pressure ratio less than 46. Also, at high compression ratios, real Humphrey cycle showed higher benefit over Joule than real PDE cycle, which showed lesser benefit.

Recently, Stathopoulos [4] performed a comprehensive analysis with a more accurate Humphrey Cycle-based PGC combustion model developed by Nalim [11] by incorporating practical losses through secondary air compression, turbine cooling, PGC inlet pressure drop and isobaric combustion loss. The study quantified the performance benefits of PGC more accurately and showed that with realistic assumptions on inlet combustor pressure drop, turbine efficiency and constant pressure combustion loss, the Humphrey cycle will most probably make sense for turbine inlet temperature above 1500°C and pressure ratio less than 25. For land based power generation in combined cycle (CC), Gulen [13] performed a real cycle analysis of a pulsed detonation engine in J-class CC and showed an efficiency increment of up to 3.3 p.p. compared to the conventional CC at a combustor pressure gain of up to 1.85. Although such studies have quantified the thermodynamic performance benefits of the PGC cycle over Joule based on the first law, while a second-law analysis to understand the primary sources of cycle irreversibilities in the PGC gas turbine was not performed.

For the optimised design of innovative PGC gas turbines, exergy analysis is an important tool that can be used to identify the sources of cycle irreversibility and generate better design guidelines. Exergy is the amount of available work that can be extracted from the system at a given thermodynamic state by bringing the system into thermal equilibrium with the surrounding through a reversible process. The traditional first-law analysis does not include the distinction between heat and work, quality of heat and work lost in adiabatic compression and expansion processes, which prevents identification of the sources of irreversibility and hinders an intuitive understanding of the effect of individual processes on the system losses. In this regard, the second law or exergy analysis focuses on the availability of work and entropy balance of components and processes and provides a much more detailed insight into the source of losses.

The sources of cycle irreversibilities in the well-established conventional GTs have been extensively studied in the past [12–14]. El-Masri [14] performed cycle analysis of the gas turbine cycle with actual chemical and thermodynamic properties and showed that the main irreversibility losses occur in the isobaric combustion process followed by turbine cooling, and comparatively, the losses due to pressure losses in the compressor are smaller [14]. For instance, at a pressure ratio of 14 and TIT of 1550 K, the losses in the combustor and turbine were 29.1% and 6.7%, respectively, of the supplied fuel exergy. Comparatively, the losses from inlet filter pressure drop, compressor and diffuser loss were less than 2.5% of fuel exergy. Similarly, Fagbenle [15] reported a combustor exergy loss of around 48% with respect to fuel exergy in a 53 MW GT combined cycle.

This study aims to understand the performance of a GT cycle with a PGC combustor with respect to a conventional counterpart from the exergy or second-law perspective. Since the combustor is the largest source of exergy losses in the gas turbine cycle, it is important to examine the exergy performance of GT cycle with pressure gain combustion. To the best of the author's

knowledge, a comprehensive exergy analysis of GT with PGC combustion at wide range of operating conditions is not available in open literature. The following sections of the paper describe the PGC combustor model, gas turbine layout, simulation methodology and the results.

2. Methodology

2.1 PGC Combustor model

PGC was represented by the constant volume model developed by Nalim [11], in this study. Figure 1(a)&(b) respectively, show the P-v and T-s diagram of a gas turbine with this PGC combustor model. The conventional Joule cycle is shown by processes 1-2-3'-4'.

Figure 1. P-v diagram (a) and T-s diagram (b) of the Humphrey cycle-based PGC model, and constant pressure combustion loss model inside PGC combustor (c)

In Fig. 1(a)&(b), processes 2-3_a-3_b define the overall pressure gain combustion process (2-3_b). It consists of a pure CVC process (2-3_a) followed by an internal expansion (3_a-3_b) inside the combustor that does not produce work and generates a steady combustor outlet state (3_b), equivalent to the mass and time-averaged conditions at the outlet of a periodic CVC process. This expansion (3_a-3_b) accounts for the flow work required to expel the products of the unsteady CVC process (2-3_a) to the steady state at the combustor outlet (3_b) [11]. This internal expansion prevents work extraction from the momentarily occurring maximum cycle temperature T_{3a} and hence, avoids performance over prediction, which occurred in some early PGC studies [8].

With reactants at state 2, combustion outlet temperature (T_{3b}) is calculated with the assumption of isobaric combustion by applying enthalpy balance between state 2 and 3_b, since state 3_b is the representative exit state of heat addition in an open thermodynamic system as per

this model [11]. This is done by iteratively solving Eq. (1) for T_{prod} using the enthalpy definitions given by Eqs. 2-5.

$$m_a h_a + m_f h_f = h_{ea}(m_a - m_f AF_s) + m_f h_s(1 + AF_s) - m_f(1 - \eta_b)LHV \quad (1)$$

$$h_a = \sum_{i=1}^5 X_{a,i} \left(h_{f,i}^o + \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_a} c_{p,i} dT \right) \quad (2)$$

$$h_f = h_{f,i}^o + \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_f} c_{p,i} dT \quad (3)$$

$$h_s = \sum_{i=1}^5 X_{s,i} \left(h_{f,i}^o + \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_{prod}} c_{p,i} dT \right) \quad (4)$$

$$h_{ea} = \sum_{i=1}^5 X_{ea,i} \left(h_{f,i}^o + \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_{prod}} c_{p,i} dT \right) \quad (5)$$

After that, the temperature at the end of the pure CVC process (T_{3a}) is calculated by iteratively solving Eq. 6 for T_{prod} using the internal energy definitions given by Eqs. 7-10 and enthalpy definitions defined above.

$$m_a u_a + m_f u_f = u_{ea}(m_a - m_f AF_s) + m_f u_s(1 + AF_s) - m_f(1 - \eta_b)LHV \quad (6)$$

$$u_a = h_a - R_a \cdot T_a \quad (7)$$

$$u_f = h_f - R_f \cdot T_f \quad (8)$$

$$u_s = h_s - R_s \cdot T_{prod} \quad (9)$$

$$u_{ea} = h_{ea} - R_{ea} \cdot T_{prod} \quad (10)$$

Pressure at the end of the pure CVC process, P_{3a} , is then calculated with the perfect gas equation using Eqs. 11 & 12 through constant specific volume assumption for the CVC process.

$$P_{3a} = \frac{R_{prod} T_{prod}}{v_{prod}} \quad (11)$$

$$v_{prod} = v_{reac} = \frac{R_{reac} T_{reac}}{P_{reac}} \quad (12)$$

Here, R_{reac} , T_{reac} and P_{reac} were calculated for the premixed reaction mixture after the inlet pressure loss in the combustor.

With T_{3a} , P_{3a} and T_{3b} known, the outlet pressure of the PGC combustion process (P_{3b}), is calculated by modelling process 3_a-3_b as an adiabatic expansion, given by Eq. 13. The value of γ in Eq. 13 was iteratively estimated at the average temperature of the expansion process.

$$\frac{P_{3b}}{P_{3a}} = \left(\frac{T_{3b}}{T_{3a}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (13)$$

Figure 1(c) shows all the processes that occur inside the PGC combustor of the gas turbine. Firstly, the inlet air and fuel are mixed, and then, the resulting flow is split into two streams, the majority of which is combusted in the primary PGC combustion mode (PGC-CVC), which contains the CVC-based PGC combustion process described in Fig. 1 (a)&(b). The remaining mass of reactants (m_{CPC}) is redirected to burn at constant pressure mode (PGC-CPC) to capture the loss due to constant pressure combustion, which occurs in all practical PGC devices.

Inside the PGC-CPC, the constant pressure combustion is assumed to occur at the peak pressure of the PGC combustion model (P_{3a} in Fig. 1(a)&(b)) [4]. The temperature at the end of this CPC combustion is calculated through enthalpy balance by solving Eq. 1-5 for T_{prod} . Then combustion products of this CPC process are adiabatically expanded to the pressure at the end of

the PGC-CVC process (P_{3b}) [4], using Eq. 13, with γ estimated iteratively at the average temperature of expansion. Both constant pressure combustion and expansion to P_{3b} of m_{CPC} occur inside the PGC-CPC in Fig. 1(c). The temperature at the end of this expansion, $T_{PGC-CPC}$ and pressure P_{3b} define the exit state of the PGC-CPC loss model shown in Fig. 1(c). Finally, the products of PGC-CVC and PGC-CPC are adiabatically mixed to produce the final outlet conditions of the PGC combustor, P_{3b} and T_{PGC} , which are also the conditions for entry in the first-stage turbine stator. This modeling the constant pressure loss is essential for a realistic cycle analysis because in all practical PGC devices, a certain amount of combustion occurs at the isobaric conditions that reduces overall benefit from PGC. In real PGC combustors, such losses result from very complex and unsteady physical phenomenon driven by combustion and gas dynamics, which makes it difficult to define the pressure at which the constant pressure combustion occurs [4,16]. Because of these challenges, a simplified model capable of capturing such losses is required for a realistic 0-D steady-state cycle analysis [4]. A detailed understanding of such modelling approaches and the associated challenges in reduced order cycle analysis of PGC cycles can be found in the literature [4,11,16].

In this work, hydrogen was used as the fuel with air as the working fluid. Air was considered as a mixture of five gases: N₂, O₂, H₂O, CO₂ and Argon. For a given combustion equivalence ratio (< 1), the product gases in Eqs. 1 & 6 consisted of products of complete stoichiometric combustion and excess unreacted air, a two-component approach typically used for gas turbine cycle analysis. The third term on the right side in Eq. 1 & 6 is the heat lost due to combustion inefficiency. For each combustion process, the outlet composition is calculated based on the equivalence ratio, and the final mixture composition at the combustor outlet enters the turbine for work production. It is important to note that the approach described by Eqs. 1 & 6 calculates combustion temperature by taking into account the variation of specific heat of individual gases with temperature, which allows capturing the real gas effect arising from higher specific heats of triatomic gases, mainly water vapour and carbon dioxide present in combustion products [17].

2.2 Turbine Cooling Model

For all three stages, the cooling flow was estimated for both stator and rotor based on the approach developed by Wilcock et al. [18] that considers cooling through internal convective cooling, film cooling and thermal barrier coating (TBC). The model allows the prediction of cooling flow ratio (Ψ) based on different cooling technology levels (CTL) expressed in terms of five parameters namely cooling flow factor (K_{cool}), internal convective cooling efficiency (η_{int}), film cooling effectiveness (ϵ_f), Biot number of turbine blade metal (Bi_{met}) and Biot number of thermal barrier coating (Bi_{TBC}) [18]. The values of these parameters used for all simulations in this work are listed in Table 1 [18,19]. For a given main gas temperature (T_g), allowable blade metal temperature (T_{bl}) and cooling flow inlet temperature ($T_{cl,in}$), the cooling effectiveness (ϵ_o) is calculated by Eq. 14 and then, Ψ is estimated from Eq. 15 using the parameters in Table 1.

$$e = \frac{(T_g - T_{bl})}{(T_g - T_{cl,in})} \quad (14)$$

$$\Psi = \frac{m_{cl}}{m_g} = \frac{K_{cool}}{(1+Bi)} \left(\frac{e - \epsilon_f [1 - \eta_{int}(1-e)]}{\eta_{int}(1-e)} \right) \quad (15)$$

Table 1: Cooling flow parameters.

Parameter	K_{cool}	η_{int}	ϵ_f	Bi_{met}	Bi_{TBC}
Value	0.045	0.75	0.45	0.15	0.40

For each cooled turbine stage, stator and rotor cooling flows are calculated separately. In the first step, the stator cooling air is mixed with the main gas flow, and the resulting mixture is expanded in the rotor. A mixing pressure drop equal to 0.07Ψ was considered for the mixing of the main gas flow and cooling flow in the stator based on the correlation developed by Horlock et al. [20]. The cooling air for the rotor is mixed after the expansion, and the resulting mixture enters the subsequent stage. This model of turbine expansion with stator and rotor cooling is widely implemented in literature and effectively represents practical trends [4,21]. It also allows stage-by-stage analysis of exergy destruction from turbine blade cooling.

2.3 Exergy Calculation

The total exergy of working fluid was calculated at each point of the cycle as the sum of mechanical, thermal and chemical exergy from Eq. 16 [22]. The reference temperature and pressure of the surrounding were 15 °C and 1 atm, respectively.

$$\varepsilon_{tot} = \varepsilon_{ph} + \varepsilon_{ch} \quad (16)$$

Physical exergy (ε_{ph}), the sum of mechanical (ε_{me}) and thermal exergy (ε_{th}) is calculated at each point from Eq. 17 using T and P obtained from thermodynamic calculations [22,23].

$$\varepsilon_{ph} = h(T,P) - h(T_0,P_0) - T_0(s(T,P) - s(T_0,P_0)) \quad (17)$$

With ε_{ph} known, mechanical exergy is calculated from Eq. 18 using reference temperature instead of the actual temperature in Eq. 17, which makes the thermal component of exergy zero in physical exergy [22]. The thermal exergy is then calculated with Eq. 19, as the difference between physical and mechanical exergy [22].

$$\varepsilon_{me} = \varepsilon_{ph}(T_0, P) = h(T_0, P) - h(T_0, P_0) - T_0(s(T_0, P) - s(T_0, P_0)) \quad (18)$$

$$\varepsilon_{th} = \varepsilon_{ph} - \varepsilon_{me} \quad (19)$$

The chemical exergy of the mixture of gases at each point is calculated from Eq. 20 using the standard chemical potential of the gas components [22].

$$\varepsilon_{ch} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 (x_i \tilde{\varepsilon}_{ch_i} + R_u T_0 x_i \ln x_i)}{MW_{mix}} - \frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}_{ch_0}}{MW_{amb}} \quad (20)$$

The exergy efficiency for each gas turbine component was calculated as the ratio of exergy recovered to exergy supplied [12,22,24]. The exergy efficiency of compressor, turbine stage and combustor was calculated using Eq. 21, 22 & 23. Note that Eq. 22 calculates exergy efficiency for a given turbine stage. The overall exergy efficiency of the entire turbine expansion was then calculated using a similar approach of exergy balance across all three stages.

$$\eta_{\varepsilon_{comp}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{out}\varepsilon_{out} + \dot{m}_{cl}\varepsilon_{cl} - \dot{m}_{in}\varepsilon_{in}}{W_{comp}} \quad (21)$$

$$\eta_{\varepsilon_{turb}} = \frac{W_{turb}}{\dot{m}_{in}\varepsilon_{in} + \dot{m}_{cl_s}\varepsilon_{cl_s} + \dot{m}_{cl_r}\varepsilon_{cl_r} - \dot{m}_{out}\varepsilon_{out}} \quad (22)$$

$$\eta_{\varepsilon_{comb}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{out}\varepsilon_{out} - \dot{m}_{a_{in}}\varepsilon_{a_{in}}}{\dot{m}_f\varepsilon_f} \quad (23)$$

The cycle thermal efficiency based on the first law principle was calculated as the ratio of net cycle work output (W_t) to the total heat addition [12,22,24], as shown in Eq 24. Similarly, the cycle exergy efficiency was calculated as the ratio of net cycle work output to the total exergy addition [12,22,24] in the cycle using Eq. 25.

$$\eta_t = \frac{W_t}{\dot{m}_f LHV} \quad (24)$$

$$\eta_\varepsilon = \frac{W_t}{\dot{m}_f \varepsilon_f} \quad (25)$$

2.4 Layout and Simulation Parameters

Two gas turbine cycle layouts, one with a PGC combustor (discussed in Fig. 1(c)) and one with a conventional Joule combustor, were used in this work. A 4% pressure drop was considered in the conventional Joule cycle combustor and polytropic efficiency of compressor and turbine stages was set to 90%. Combustion efficiency for both cycles was maintained as 99.5%. For the PGC layout, two cases with different values of combustor losses were investigated, which are shown in Table 2. In the first case (PGC1), an inlet pressure drop in the PGC combustor is considered the same as that in the Joule combustor and complete combustion is assumed to occur in pressure gain combustion mode (PGC-CVC in Fig. 1(c)). Therefore, PGC1 is an optimistic case that provides the upper limit of the PGC performance. In the second case (PGC2), more realistic values of PGC combustor losses were introduced in the cycle [4,5,25,26], where 20% of reactants were burnt at constant pressure combustion mode (PGC-CPC in Fig. 1(c)) and inlet pressure drop was increased to 15%, to understand the impact of realistic losses on cycle exergy performance.

Table 2. Loss parameters for the two cases of PGC gas turbine cycle.

	m_{CPC} (%)	$\Delta P_{PGC \text{ inlet}}$ (%)	η_{pPGC} (%)
PGC1	0	4	90
PGC2	20	15	90

The turbine in both layouts consisted of 3 cooled stages, and the cooling air was bled from the compressor outlet. Figure 2 shows the layout of the gas turbine with PGC combustor. An additional secondary air compressor is required to compensate for pressure gain to supply the cooling air for the first turbine stage stator. Due to the temperature drop from expansion, the cooling flow in T3 was zero except for some conditions of low-pressure ratios at TIT = 1700°C, when the entry temperature of the gas in T3 was higher than the allowable blade metal temperature of 825°C. The pressure at the exit of T3 was 1 atm, the ambient reference pressure, for all simulations. Also, all primary cycle simulations were performed with turbine cooling (unless stated otherwise), except for some cases for comparison with uncooled turbines for investigating the effect of turbine cooling.

Figure 2. Cycle layout of the cooled gas turbine with PGC combustor.

Simulations were performed with both layouts at two TIT values of 1300°C and 1700°C at compressor pressure ratios from 5-40. Table 3 provides the values of important cycle input parameters. Supply conditions of hydrogen fuel were kept the same at 40 bar and 15°C for all simulations. The lower heating value of fuel (LHV) was 120 MJ/kg and fuel exergy at the combustor inlet (ϵ_f) was 121 MJ/kg, including the effect of the physical exergy due to the pressure. Air was supplied to the compressor at reference ISO conditions; therefore, the total exergy of inlet air was zero. All the simulations were performed in WTEMP (Web-based Thermo-Economic Modular Program) software developed by Thermochemical Power Group (TPG) at the University of Genova. It is a modular and flexible tool for thermo-economic analysis and optimisation of innovative energy systems [19].

Table 3. Simulation parameters.

Component	Symbol	Value
Compressor polytropic efficiency (%)	η_{comp}	90
Turbine polytropic efficiency (%)	η_{turb}	90
SAC polytropic efficiency (%)	η_{SAC}	90
Allowable blade metal temperature (°C)	T_{bl}	825
Combustion efficiency (%)	η_{comb}	99.5
Joule combustor pressure drop (%)	ΔP_{Joule}	4
Mechanical/Electrical Efficiency (%)	η_{m-e}	98.5
Fuel lower heating value (MJ/kg)	LHV	120
Fuel supply pressure (bar)	$P_{f, in}$	40
Reference Temperature (°C)	T_{ref}	15
Reference Pressure (bar)	P_{ref}	1.013

3. Results and discussion

This section describes the results of all the simulations for the two PGC cycles and one Joule cycle performed at the conditions mentioned above. For the sake of representation, key cycle parameters for the PGC1 cycle at TIT=1700°C and $\pi=20$ are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Key cycle parameters for PGC1 at TIT=1700°C and $\pi=20$.

3.1 Cycle Performance

Figure 4(a)&(b) show the cycle efficiencies and Fig. 4(c) shows the pressure gain across the combustor. For all cycles, the exergy efficiency is slightly lower than thermal efficiency because the total exergy input into the cycle is higher than the total heat input due to contribution from the fuel mechanical exergy at 40 bar supply pressure. Looking at PGC cycles, the optimistic PGC1 cycle shows higher thermal and exergy efficiency than the Joule cycle at all operating conditions because of higher pressure gain compared to PGC2 (Fig. 4(c)), which increases turbine expansion ratio and work output. PGC1 shows the highest pressure gain of 0.77 at $\pi=5$ and TIT=1700°C. Also, since pressure gain in the combustor is directly proportional to temperature rise across it, the benefit over Joule decreases with increasing π because of the simultaneous increase in combustor inlet temperature that reduces pressure gain, for a fixed TIT [4,8]. Due to the same reason pressure gain for the high TIT of 1700°C is higher than that for 1300°C TIT (Fig. 4(c)), leading to higher efficiency benefit of PGC1 over Joule at high TIT. At the pressure ratio of 20, the thermal and exergy efficiency of PGC1 is higher than Joule by around 3.9 p.p. & 5.6 p.p. for TIT of 1300°C & 1700°C, respectively.

Figure 4. Cycle thermal and exergy efficiency as a function of compressor pressure ratio: TIT=1300°C (a) and TIT=1700°C (b), and non-dimensionalized pressure gain in combustor (c)

Secondly, the PGC2 cycle, which contains realistic assumptions of losses in the PGC combustor (Table 2), shows a significant drop in efficiency compared to PGC1. A 20% constant pressure loss lowers combustor outlet temperature for a given fuel flow or requires more flow to attain the same TIT. On the other hand, a 15% inlet pressure drop in the PGC2 combustor reduces the pressure gain (compared to PGC1) for both TITs (Fig. 4 (c)), lowering the turbine work output. In fact, at TIT =1300°C, the low pressure gain at high pressure ratio ($\pi \geq 30$) in PGC2 is not able to compensate for 15% inlet pressure loss and so the final outlet pressure remains lower than the inlet pressure. The combined effect of these two losses reduces the efficiency of PGC2 with respect to PGC1, at all cycle conditions. Furthermore, at low π , the benefit from pressure gain in PGC2 is able to compensate for these losses, leading to higher efficiency than Joule. But, as the pressure gain is reduced with increasing π , the effect of these losses on the cycle becomes dominant, resulting in a breakeven point with Joule at $\pi = 20$ & 35 for TIT=1300°C & 1700°C, respectively. The breakeven point occurs at a higher pressure ratio for high TIT because of higher pressure gain that can maintain efficiency benefit till higher π .

Figure 5 shows the specific mechanical exergy at the combustor outlet for all cases. It is important to note that for all cases with positive pressure gain, the mechanical exergy at the

combustor outlet is higher than the Joule counterpart. This is an important characteristic of the PGC cycle which eventually gets reflected in terms of higher turbine work. At TIT=1700°C and minimum $\pi=5$, the mechanical exergy of PGC1 and PGC2 cycles is higher than Joule by 43 kJ/kg (38.6%) and 34.7 kJ/kg (31.15%), respectively. The corresponding values at $\pi=20$ are 24.5 kJ/kg (11.4%) and 15.1 kJ/kg (7%). Only in the case of the PGC2 cycle at TIT=1300°C and $\pi=40$, the mechanical exergy at the combustor outlet is marginally lower than that in Joule (Fig. 5(a)) because of the combustor pressure drop being slightly more than Joule (Fig. 4(c)).

Figure 6. Combustor equivalence ratio (a) and specific chemical exergy at combustor outlet (b) for all cases.

Figure 5. Specific mechanical exergy at combustor outlet: TIT=1300°C (a) and TIT=1700°C (b)

Figure 6(a) shows the overall combustor equivalence ratio for all cases, and the observations are intuitive. The equivalence ratio is higher for higher TIT, and for a given TIT, it decreases with π because of a reduction in allowable temperature rise across the combustor. The equivalence ratio of PGC1 is same as Joule because, its outlet temperature (T_{3b} in Fig. 1(a)&(b)) is calculated with the assumption of isobaric combustor, as described in section 2.1. For PGC2, in which 20% reactants are burned at constant pressure combustion mode, the equivalence ratio is higher

because introduction of CPC loss in the PGC combustor reduces the combustion outlet temperature, and therefore, more fuel is required to attain the desired TIT. Due to these reasons, the chemical exergy at the combustor exit presented in Fig. 6(b) is self-explanatory. The magnitude of chemical exergy is negligible compared to the mechanical exergy in Fig. 5.

The specific exergy input in the cycle and the specific net work produced are shown in Fig. 7 for all operating conditions. Firstly, comparing the net cycle work (W_t), PGC1 and PGC2 cycles generate more work than Joule at all pressure ratios and TIT values. Even at TIT=1300°C and $\pi > 20$, where PGC2 is less efficient than Joule (Fig. 4(a)), the net cycle work is still higher. This observation is consistent with recent studies [4,19] and shows an important advantage of PGC cycles, as some design decisions can be driven by the need for more specific work than efficiency alone. Moreover, the optimum pressure ratio corresponding to maximum specific work is lower for the PGC cycles [4,19]. Looking into exergy input, the exergy added in all cycles decreases with the pressure ratio because of the efficiency increase. (Fig. 4(a) and (b)).

Figure 7. Specific exergy input and specific net work of the entire cycle as a function of compressor pressure ratio: TIT=1300°C (a) and TIT=1700°C (b).

Comparing the PGC cycles with Joule, the specific exergy input in PGC2 is higher due to more heat addition. For TIT=1300°C, although the exergy input in PGC1 and Joule cycle appears to be the same in Fig. 7(a), on close observation, it can be seen that the values in PGC1 are slightly lower than Joule, and the difference is higher at high pressure ratios. This effect is stronger at TIT=1700°C in Fig. 7(b) and it is because of the less fuel addition in PGC with the increasing cooling flow that decreases combustion airflow and, consequently, the fuel flow for the set TIT. Figure 8(a) shows the total turbine cooling flow as a percentage of compressor inlet airflow. For TIT=1700°C, the cooling flows are more than twice that for TIT=1300°C. The higher cooling flow of PGC1 compared to PGC2 is because of its higher pressure gain (Fig. 5(a)), which requires more compression of cooling flow in SAC, as shown in Fig. 8(b). The resulting higher temperature of cooling flow at the turbine inlet requires more cooling flow to keep the blade metal temperature within the allowable limit (Eq. 15). For the same reason, PGC2 requires more cooling flow than the Joule cycle. In general, W_{SAC} , the work required by the Secondary Air Compressor, reduces with π due to decreasing pressure gain (Fig. 5(a)) that requires less additional compression ratio in SAC. However, W_{SAC} shows minima with π for PGC1 at TIT=1700°C because, at high compressor pressure ratios and high TIT, the cooling flow increases significantly due to additional temperature rise in SAC, which has a stronger effect in SAC work consumption than its decreasing

pressure ratio with π . Lastly, it should also be noted that work consumed by SAC is less than 2.1% of that required by the main compressor for all operating conditions. This increased energy consumption that is introduced to manage the PGC cycles, is more than compensated by the extra power produced by the turbine in presence of the pressure gain.

Figure 8. Total turbine cooling flow as percentage of compressor inlet flow (a) and Secondary air compression work as percentage of primary compressor work (b)

3.2 Effect of pressure gain combustion

This section describes the effect of pressure gain in exergy destruction during the combustion process. Figure 9 shows the specific exergy destruction in the compressor, combustor and turbine with respect to the mass flow of air entering the compressor. The irreversibility for the compressor remains the same for all cycles and only increases slightly with the π .

Figure 9. Specific exergy destruction or irreversibility of cycle components as a function of compressor pressure ratio: TIT=1300°C (a) and TIT=1700°C (b). For turbine, total exergy destroyed in all three stages is presented.

For both TITs, the combustor is the highest source of exergy loss for all pressure ratios, as would be expected in gas turbines [14,15,27], and it is also evident from Fig. 10 which shows the exergy efficiency of all components. Fig. 9 and 10 show that among all three cycles, PGC1 performs

the best in minimising exergy destruction during combustion, due to the effect of pressure gain. Although the specific exergy destroyed by the turbine is more than the compressor (Fig. 9), its exergy efficiency is still higher, due to higher exergy input.

Figure 10. Exergy efficiency of compressor, combustor and turbine as a function of compressor pressure ratio: TIT=1300°C (a) and TIT=1700°C (b).

For both TITs, although PGC1 has the same equivalence ratio as Joule (Fig. 6(a)), it recovers more exergy because the pressure gain increases the mechanical exergy at the combustor outlet (Fig. 5). Therefore, PGC1 has the least exergy loss and consequently, highest exergy efficiency among the three cycles (at all operating conditions). Thus, it can be inferred that for the same equivalence ratio, an increase in pressure during combustion can minimise exergy loss from the largest source of exergy destruction in conventional gas turbines, i.e. the heat addition process. In the case of PGC2, it has a lesser increment in mechanical exergy due to lesser pressure gain than PGC1, and therefore, it destroys more exergy, leading to lower exergy efficiency compared to PGC1. However, despite the positive pressure gain, exergy destruction in PGC2 is higher than in Joule. This can be understood through the effect of constant pressure combustion loss. With 20% of reactants burning at CPC mode, the PGC combustor requires a higher equivalence ratio (Fig. 6(a)) i.e. a higher exergy input in the combustor (Fig. 7) for the same temperature rise. In the case of PGC2, this adverse effect of constant pressure combustion loss is stronger than the beneficial effect of pressure gain, due to which, despite pressure gain, it fails to perform better than the Joule combustor in terms of exergy recovery. This underlines the importance of minimising the CPC or deflagration losses in PGC devices.

3.3 Effect of turbine blade cooling

After the combustor, turbine cooling is the largest source of irreversibility or exergy destruction in gas turbines [14,15], which can also be seen in Fig. 9. In particular, for TIT=1700°C, the total exergy destruction in all cooled turbine stages is twice that in the main compressor. Figure 11(a) & (b) compares the total exergy destruction of the cooled gas turbine (used for the results discussed so far) with that of an uncooled gas turbine. For uncooled gas turbines, the total turbine exergy destruction follows the trend of the overall expansion ratio which is determined by the pressure gain in the combustor (Fig. 4(c)). When blade cooling is introduced, turbine irreversibility increases significantly, and the increment is very high for 1700°C TIT. Also, for both

TITs, the turbine irreversibility in the PGC cycles is higher than Joule due to the larger expansion ratio. However, on close inspection of Fig. 11(a) & (b), an interesting observation can be made that, in going from uncooled to cooled turbine, the increase in turbine irreversibility is slightly lower in PGC cycles than in Joule. For instance, at $\pi=20$ and $TIT=1300^{\circ}\text{C}$, the total turbine irreversibility increases by 16.5%, 15.22% and 14.22%, respectively, for the Joule, PGC2 and PGC1 cycles, compared to their uncooled counterpart. Similarly, at $\pi=20$ and $TIT=1700^{\circ}\text{C}$, the corresponding increase is 51%, 43.13% and 40.43%, respectively for the Joule, PGC2 and PGC1. Since these values follow the pressure gain discussed previously, it can be conjectured that due to the high expansion ratio resulting from pressure gain, the percentage increase of turbine irreversibility from blade cooling in a PGC cycle is less than that in Joule. Moving further, in PGC gas turbine cycles, turbine cooling introduces an additional contribution of irreversibility due to SAC. However, exergy loss from SAC presented in Fig. 11(c) shows that compared to other components (Fig. 9), the secondary air compressor destroys negligible exergy, which will also be expected due to very low W_{SAC} (Fig. 8(b)).

Figure 11. Total specific exergy destruction in all turbine stages for cooled and uncooled gas turbine cycle: $TIT=1300^{\circ}\text{C}$ (a) and $TIT=1700^{\circ}\text{C}$ (b), and specific exergy destruction in secondary air compressor (c).

The exergy efficiency of the cooled and uncooled cycles is shown in Fig. 12. Without turbine blade cooling, all cycles show nearly the same turbine exergy efficiency for a given operating condition. But the overall turbine exergy efficiency is higher for the cycle with high TIT of 1700°C than 1300°C . This is because with high TIT or a high expansion ratio, the turbine adiabatic efficiency increases, for a fixed polytropic efficiency leading to higher work generation with less loss, which then gets manifested in the form of higher exergy efficiency. The picture changes completely, as blade cooling is introduced and the cooled cycle at $TIT=1700^{\circ}\text{C}$ shows less exergy efficiency than 1300°C , because of very high cooling requirements (Fig. 8 (a)) and associated losses. With large cooling flows, the work output reduces substantially, resulting in lower exergy efficiency. At low pressure ratios for $TIT 1700^{\circ}\text{C}$ cycle, PGC1 and PGC2 are exergetically more efficient than Joule, because the disadvantage from the high cooling flow is partially compensated by a high expansion ratio due to high pressure gain (Fig. 4(c)) at these low pressure ratios.

Figure 12. Total turbine exergy efficiency for cooled and uncooled gas turbine cycles: TIT=1300°C (a) and TIT=1700°C (b) .

4. Conclusion

The present work compared the exergy performance of the conventional Joule cycle with two different PGC cycles, one with optimistic combustor losses and the other with realistic combustor losses. The following conclusions can be drawn from the work.

1. In an optimistic case, without losses, both exergy and thermal efficiency of the PGC cycle show higher benefit over Joule at low compressor pressure ratios. However, when realistic values of inlet pressure drop and constant pressure loss are considered, both exergy and thermal efficiency fall rapidly, and the breakeven point with Joule occurs at a higher compressor ratio for a higher TIT cycle.
2. For the same π , TIT and equivalence ratio, a combustor with pressure gain recovers more exergy than a Joule combustor, thereby minimising exergy loss in the heat addition process, which is the largest source of irreversibility in gas turbines. For example, $\pi=20$, TIT=1700°C and PGC combustor with a pressure ratio of 1.35, the exergy efficiency of PGC combustor is 79.6% compared to 77.9% in the case of Joule combustor.
3. As stated by other authors, PGC cycles present always higher specific work than Joule cycles. Moreover, the optimum pressure ratio corresponding to maximum specific work is lower for the PGC cycles and correspond to the area of major efficiency enhancement with respect to the Joule.
4. For the same π , TIT, when the PGC combustor operates at a higher equivalence ratio due to 15% inlet pressure drop and 20% constant pressure combustion loss, the PGC combustor destroys more exergy than conventional combustor at all operating conditions; however, because of positive pressure gain (although very low due to losses), the benefit on the cycle is retained at lower pressure ratios.
5. In going from uncooled to cooled turbine, the percentage increase in turbine irreversibility from blade cooling is slightly lower in the PGC cycle (even with combustor losses) than in Joule. For instance, even at losses mentioned in point 4, turbine irreversibility increases by 43.13% in the PGC cycle, compared to 51% in Joule.
6. With high combustor pressure gain at low cycle pressure ratios, expansion of the cooled turbine is exergetically more efficient in the PGC cycle than Joule.

7. The contribution of the secondary air compressor in the total exergy destruction of the PGC cycle is negligible.

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Symbols

AF	air-fuel ratio
c_p	specific heat capacity [$\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]
h	specific enthalpy [Jkg^{-1}]
$h_{f,i}^0$	enthalpy of formation [Jkg^{-1}]
m_{CPC}	degree of constant pressure combustion [%]
m	mass flow rate (kgs^{-1})
η	efficiency [%]
η_{pPGC}	polytropic efficiency of internal expansion [%]
P	pressure [Pa]
R	gas constant [$\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]
R_u	gas constant [$\text{Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]
T	temperature [K]
v	specific volume [m^3kg^{-1}]
W	specific work [Jkg^{-1}]
X	mass fraction
x	mole fraction
γ	ratio of specific heats
ΔP_{PGCin}	PGC inlet pressure loss [%]
ε	specific exergy [Jkg^{-1}]
$\tilde{\varepsilon}$	specific exergy [Jmol^{-1}]
π	compressor pressure ratio

Subscripts

a	air
ch	chemical
cl	cooling
$comb$	burner
$comp$	compressor
ea	excess air
f	fuel
i	gas species
in	inlet
me	mechanical
out	outlet
p	polytropic
ph	physical
$prod$	combustion products
$reac$	combustion reactants
r	rotor
s	stator
st	stoichiometric

<i>t</i>	thermal
<i>turb</i>	turbine
<i>tot</i>	total
<i>0</i>	reference ambient conditions

Acronyms

<i>CPC</i>	constant pressure combustion
<i>CVC</i>	constant volume combustion
<i>LHV</i>	lower heating value of fuel [Jkg^{-1}]
<i>MW</i>	molecular weight [kgmol^{-1}]
<i>PGC</i>	pressure gain combustion
<i>SAC</i>	secondary air compressor
<i>TIT</i>	turbine inlet temperature [K]

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